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USE OF ICT IN THE PROFESSIONAL WORK OF TEACHER IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ESTABLISHMENT

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Abstract. *The article presents the results of research of essence of use of ICT in modern practice of preschool education. On the basics of theoretical analyses, the meaning of the use of ICT in professional work of a teacher in preschool educational establishment is revealed. The pedagogical experiment was carried out in 2 stages during 2019–2020 years: ascertaining and preparatory, it involved pedagogical staff of 6 preschool institutions of Cherkasy region and Pereiaslav of Kyiv region (46 people in total). On results of ascertaining diagnostics, the stage of readiness of pedagogical workers of preschool educational establishments to the use of ICT in personal professional work was determined. It showed the direct relation with the level of formation of their informative-communicative competence. The content of work at preparatory stage is revealed, the task of using ICT in realization of the basic task of development, education and training of preschool children. During the conducted research-experimental work the efficiency of application of the following organizational and pedagogical conditions is proved: managing the process of use of ICT in the work of preschool educational establishment; developing IC-competence in teachers of preschool educational establishments and their preparation for use of informative-communicative technologies in professional work.*

Key words: *preschool education, informative-communicative technologies (ICT), organizational-pedagogical conditions of use of ICT; professional work of preschool teachers.*

Всмысл

Introduction

In the Law of Ukraine “On Education” the necessity of the universal use of ICT in educational process in various educational institutions are highlighted. This may become the instrument of ensuring success of Ukrainian education system. The article offers that, in order to improve the quality of education, use of ICT should move from single projects into systematical process which covers all aspects of education (Law of Ukraine “On Education”, 2017). It is important to mention that the results of analyzed research prove that ICT (informative-communicative technologies) are appropriate to use both in educational work of teachers and in methodical work (Almerich, Orellana, Suárez-Rodríguez, & Díaz-García, 2016; Machekhina, 2017; Otterborn, Schönborn, & Hultén, 2019). ICT belongs to

the system of general scientific and pedagogical knowledge, they appeared and develop on the border of general innovations, methodology, theoretical basis of many sciences. On the current stage ICT is one of the dominating tendencies in organization of educational process and in preschool educational establishments, in particular (Andriushchenko, Lokhvytska, Rudenko & Dudnyk, 2021; Eurén, 2018; Hardersen, 2012; Masoumi, 2015). From the mentioned above, scientific problem of current state of use of ICT in professional work of preschool teacher is outlined. It will be the subject of initiated research.

Методи і методики дослідження ***Methods and Techniques of the Research***

In order to clarify the essence of use of ICT by teachers of preschool educational establishments in their professional work, ascertaining diagnostic of the state of their readiness was done. On the grounds of the obtained results, methodology of formative experiment with the raise of awareness of teachers as for the use of ICT in organization of educational process with children of preschool age was developed.

Результати ***Results***

Experimental work, which took place during 2019–2020 years, involved teachers from 6 preschool educational establishments of Cherkasy region and Pereiaslav, Kyiv region (in total 46 people), who were teaching, upbringing and developing children of preschool age, was directed into research of organizational-pedagogical conditions of digitalization of preschool education. Research-experimental work was aimed to investigate potential possibilities of informative-communicative technologies for improvement of the quality of education, upbringing and development of children of preschool age. Pedagogical experiment was made in 2 stages: ascertaining and preparatory.

On ascertaining stage of research-experimental work on the basis of theoretical analysis the *main directions* of use of informative-communicative technologies were revealed. These directions may simultaneously be considered as *organization-pedagogical conditions*, in particular:

- managing the process of use of informative-communicative technologies in the work of preschool educational establishment;
- developing IC-competence in teachers of preschool educational establishments and their preparation for use of informative-communicative technologies in professional work;
- using informative-communicative technologies in organization of education, upbringing and development of children of preschool age.

At the same stage of the experiment ascertaining diagnostics of the condition of readiness of teachers of the preschool educational establishment for the use of ICT on work was made. According to our convictions, the condition of teachers' readiness for use of ICT in professional activities depends on the level of formation of their informative-communicative competence. Diagnostics of IC-competence of teachers is made according to the criteria and corresponding indicators: *epistemological* (comprehensive knowledge about modern informative-communicative technologies, means of ICT used in preschool education and in personal professional development); *motivation* (awareness of ICT significance for improvement of the quality of preschool education, positive motivation to

the use of ICT on work, ambition for professional self-development with the help of ICT); *activity* (level of proficiency of modern informative-communicative technologies, experience of ICT use in the fulfillment of preschool education, experience of professional development by means of ICT).

According to the results of ascertaining diagnostics all the respondents showed: they can write and edit textual information, make and send email messages with the help of the Internet, download some materials (resources) from the Internet to a CD and vice versa, print information with the help of printer etc. At the same time 48.5% of people questioned mentioned that they have some difficulties while doing multimedia presentations, 59.7% – using electronic data bases in pedagogical sphere, 81.3% – in creating personal professional electronic portfolio, 58.9% – entering electronic conferences and virtual professional communities. Unfortunately, 53.4% of teachers stated that for different reasons in their work they use traditional means of preschool education and their professional self-development. Besides, 60.2% of respondents demonstrated very limited ideas about using modern ICT in personal professional work. In general, diagnostic data showed *high level* of IC-awareness 5.4% of teachers in preschool educational establishments, *sufficient level* – 34.4% and *insufficient level* of IC-competence was discovered in 60.2% of teachers.

Taking into account the results of the diagnostics the content was determined and strategic planning of *management of the process of ICT use in the work of preschool educational establishment* on the next preparing stage of experiment was done. It was planned in all the establishments in the experiment to create material and technical conditions for effective use of ICT in different spheres of preschool educational establishments; search of pedagogical software tools that are necessary for quality preschool education and other digital educational resources; prepare teacher for the use of ICT during organization of preschool education and personal professional development; creation and/or storage of methodical ensuring of the process of ICT implementation in the sphere of preschool education.

The website became the center of informative-communicative educational space of every experimental preschool establishment, the main sections of which were such pages: main page; history of the establishment; administration; pedagogical staff; establishment's working plan; news; achievements; photos; methodological work; video presentations; information for parents; feedback (contacts, virtual consulting room).

With the aim of IC-competence development in teachers and their preparation to the *use of ICT in professional work* in experimental preschool educational establishments practical seminars in full-time and distant form were organized. The topics of seminars were “Modern informative technologies”, “Methods of using computer games in preschool education”, “Methods of creation of multimedia presentations for preschool education”, “Methods of creating digital didactic and developmental materials by means of Microsoft Office”, “ICT for learning Math by preschoolers”, “ICT for learning alphabet and speech development of preschoolers”, “Services Web 2.0 in preschool education”, “Google forms in work with parents of preschool children”, “Creation of web portfolios using Word and PowerPoint”, “Cloud technologies for professional self-development of preschool teachers”.

Distant practical seminars of the stated topics were conducted in the form of webinars. Such platforms as OpenMeetings, BigBlueButton, Microsoft Lync, Adobe Connect were used during the experiment for the organization of webinars. The most comfortable for the participants of research-experimental work was platform Adobe Connect, because its software allows teachers to take part in the webinar from any place with the help of their mobile devices. Besides, platform Adobe Connect provides with qualified video- and voice

connection, text messages in chat, gives an opportunity to use a “white board”, demonstrate “Desktop” and active software applications from the computer of the “speaker”, exchange Microsoft Office (PDF) documents, apply a toolkit for questionnaires and votes among the participants of the webinar. The participants of the experiment used Skype connection to provide individual consultation upon request on different aspects of ICT implementation into the sphere of preschool education.

Besides, preschool educational establishments formed creative groups of teachers based on the main areas of use of ICT for the improvement of preschool education quality. For the effective work of each of the creative groups, according to the tasks of experiment, the goals were specified; developed instructions about the order of organization and holding research-experimental work, which were approved by publishing of the corresponding order in the preschool educational establishment. The efforts of teachers of every creative group were sent for processing scientific-methodical literature, learning and analyzing pedagogical experience on the questions of use of ICT. With the aim of creation of personal digital resources for education, upbringing and development of children of preschool age, participants of creative groups were recommended to use materials from the website “Funny alphabet”, “Thematic collection of drawings” (in English), “Collection of cognitive materials for children”, “Children of Ukraine”, “Library of the Ukrainian literature”, “Governmental site for young citizens”, “Children’s site”, “Children’s fairy tales”, “Children’s portal Pustunchik”, “Children’s site Levko”, “Storyteller” and other. On the results of the work of creative groups of teachers in preschool educational establishments bank of electronic resources of fairy tales, cartoons, documentary movies of cognitive character for children, developmental gaming programs, crosswords, songs and melodies, presentations for realization of all the mentioned above educational lines was accumulated etc.

Висновки *Conclusions*

Results of the completed research give the grounds to state significant potential of ICT for the development of informative-communicative competence of teachers of preschool educational establishments, organization of education of children of preschool age, establishment of partnership interaction with preschoolers’ parents. Figured out that strategic planning of *management of the process of ICT use in the work of preschool educational establishment* is one of the priorities of creation of psychologically convenient educational environment in preschool educational establishments and important resource of improvement of the quality of modern preschool education. It is proved that *developing IC-competence in teachers of preschool educational establishments and their preparation for use of ICT in professional work* is provided by conducting seminars in full-time and distant form were organized with involvement of various digital services.

The perspectives of further experimental work will consist of such stages: formative and control, which will give the opportunity to determine effectiveness of ICT implementation and created and systematized, by teachers, bank of electronic resources for teaching and developing children of preschool age and raise of level of their personal professional work.

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